

THE POSSIBILITY INTRODUCING OF THE MOBILITY AS A SERVICE IN THE CITY OF PRISHTINA AND IN SOME SURROUNDING AREAS

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Abstract

In this paper, is addressed the possibility of introducing mobility as a service (MaaS), in Prishtina city and in some neighborhoods, in order to decrease personal car use, improve of air quality in the city, decrease passenger's stress, and many other things. The methodology used to achieve the intended results was through survey carried out in the field. The survey data was designed to study the stakeholders willingness to be part of MaaS and type integration, and as a conclusion, stakeholders from the survey area are ready to join the MaaS service, first with the first level of integration then with the highest level of integration. The data from the survey are analysed using SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) software.

Keywords: mobility as a service; type's integration; Prishtina; willingness to join MaaS

INTRODUCTION

The problems of road traffic jams, degradation of the environment in form of increased air pollution and the need of transport to use significant urban space, which is mainly result of excessive use of automobile in many cities today, has significantly impacted the quality of life of its citizens.

As result of such trends, many cities have been investing in environmentally friendly transport modes such as public transport, cycling and walking infrastructure. This policy of promotion of sustainable urban transport is a policy that the city of Prishtina, Republic of Kosovo, is also pursuing.

In recent years, the concept Mobility as a Service - MaaS has been noted as one of the ways to support the efforts toward sustainable transport, especially for reducing the use and ownership of personal cars.

Given the potential of MaaS, a survey has been done in Prishtina in order to examine the possibility for MaaS concept implementation.

In this survey total 678 questionnaires from stakeholders were identified and 132 have been obtained. The entities included into the survey were: a public transport operator, private transport operators, and train transport operator, information and communications technology (ICT) service providers, rent a car services; taxi services, and rent a bike services.

The results show that, regardless of the fact that there are a number of obstacles to the implementation of MaaS, the willingness to join this service exists, and the implementation can be done gradually, starting from the basic level of integration to the highest level.

REVIEW OF EXISTING SCIENTIFIC ARTICLES ON MAAS

MaaS impacts are even stronger when fleets of shared modes are introduced into the network. In fact, integration of shared modes may even allow efficiency

gains on the supply side, when used to provide accessibility to areas, in which demand is too low to support line-based public transportation. [1]

Regarding people's willingness to use MaaS packages, the results show, that even though respondents do not prefer shared modes in their MaaS plans, a significant number of them are willing to subscribe to plans that include these modes. Once they have subscribed, over 60% of them indicated that they would be willing to try transportation modes that they previously did not use if their MaaS plans included them. These initial results show evidence that MaaS bundles can indeed be used as a mobility management tool to introduce more travelers to shared modes [2], except of other attributes of the MaaS packages, as a stick measure, the increase in parking tariffs seems promising to get employees out of their cars. An increase of €2.0–2.5/hour could bring a desirable modal shift, nearly 50%. [3], while households with two or more children were significantly less likely to subscribe to MaaS than households with up to one child. This is reasonable as the demand for a private car and its convenience (e.g., available at any time and able to install child car restraints on it) increases with household children numbers. [4]. In terms of opportunities and barriers to multimodal cities about attitudes towards mobility as a service, noted, "There are a number of factors that make specific modes unattractive to certain individuals, which can be improved by targeted strategies. Overall, there was a positive attitude towards the role MaaS could play in helping behavior change and the decrease in private vehicle dependence. It is also clear, that there could be supporting policies that make it easier and more desirable to use the various multimodal solutions [5]

As for the possibility of leaving a private car, the results show that private car and motorcycle users are not significantly attracted by MaaS strategies, while individuals engaged with public transport and shared mobility services are open to their adoption. This means

that MaaS policy scenarios should mainly focus on reducing individuals' car/motorcycle dependence by providing appealing mobility alternatives and integrating all the aspects of the travel experience: planning, booking, payment, and (real-time) information [6], regarding the reduction of CO₂ MaaS can lead to sustainable reductions in mobility and CO₂ emissions from the private car sector, ranging from 2.5 to 50%, if the vehicle capacity can be optimised and technologies enable the use of green fuel. Second, the potential reduction in private car usage and CO₂ emissions depend on policies and the receptiveness of the public transport sector, for example, by supporting MaaS implementation and green vehicles, data sharing and service integration.[7]

THE RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this research, two survey methods are used to collect the data. The first was an online survey via Survey Monkey, and the second was one-on-one interviews in-person with stakeholders. Via Survey-monkey.com, the questionnaire was sent to 57 respondents, and we found their email addresses in Agency of Business Registration, which represent 13 Rent a Car and 44 IT Companies. From them, just 10 respondents answered the questionnaire; from nine were IT companies and one was rent a Car. The questionnaire was online active for one month from December 17, 2020 until January 17, 2021. The time that was spent by respondents was 10 minutes.

Parallel to the first method was also the second method, which was the interviews with stakeholders.

In total, 678 stakeholders were identified from them in interview 132, as follows: public transport operator was one, private transport operator was 24, train transport operator was one, information and communications technology (ICT) service provider was 418, Rent a Car was 194, taxi services, which operate as a company, were 39, and Rent a Bike exists as just one provider near Germia Park, which works in the spring and summer seasons. The interviews with stakeholders were done by me and assisted by one other person.

THE RESULTS OF THE SURVEY

The questions of the survey in total were 36, while the stakeholders that were identified are: public and private transport operators by bus; train transport operator; information and communications technology (ICT) service providers; taxi service providers; rent-a-car service providers; and rent-a-bike service providers.

The analysis is done through factor analysis, which is one of the multivariate statistical techniques that is widely used to reduce the number of variables that are related to each other by a small number of important factors that are independent of each other, grouping variables that have high correlations with each other, and discovering the structure of the relation of variables, in other words, classifying the variables. In our case, the factor analysis was applied to 21 variables, it is mean the 21 questions in the questionnaire (in appendix 1), from number 13 up to 19 and from 23 up to 36. Data set suitability assessment is realized through KMO and the Barlett test.

Table 1

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.657
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	542.052
	df	153
	Sig.	.000

From the table above, it can be seen that the KMO Test has a value above the allowed limit of $65.7% > 50%$, and we can say that the data set is suitable for factor analysis. The value of the Barlett test is Sig. = .000, a result that is less than 0.05. This means that there are high correlations between variables; in other words, our data set is convenient and valid. Through factor analysis, variables that do not have a high degree of 0.5 are removed from the data set. In the first analysis, three variables were removed from the data set, while in the second attempt, all remaining variables had a value higher than 0.5.

Given the total variance, we can determine the number of important factors. The total variance shows what percentage of the model explains all the variables taken together in the analysis. In our case, the first factor explains 11.751% of the total variance. The first and second factors together explain the variance of 23.088% and so on, while the six factors together explain the variance of 61,664%.

Eigen value (eigenvalues): Eigen value accepts important factors that are greater than 1.

Table 2

Number of factors related to Eigen value and explanatory percentage of variance

Component	Total Variance Explained								
	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.724	20.686	20.686	3.724	20.686	20.686	2.115	11.751	11.751
2	2.033	11.296	31.982	2.033	11.296	31.982	2.041	11.337	23.088
3	1.553	8.630	40.613	1.553	8.630	40.613	1.945	10.805	33.893
4	1.449	8.049	48.662	1.449	8.049	48.662	1.764	9.798	43.690
5	1.254	6.964	55.626	1.254	6.964	55.626	1.643	9.128	52.818
6	1.087	6.038	61.664	1.087	6.038	61.664	1.592	8.846	61.664
7	.997	5.537	67.201						
8	.915	5.081	72.282						
9	.754	4.189	76.471						
10	.641	3.564	80.034						
11	.615	3.417	83.451						
12	.556	3.089	86.540						
13	.520	2.888	89.428						
14	.491	2.729	92.156						
15	.483	2.683	94.840						
16	.375	2.085	96.924						
17	.307	1.703	98.627						
18	.247	1.373	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Whereas, the grouping of variables that are most important under one factor can be seen in the table below.

Table 3

The grouping of variables

	Rotated Component Matrix ^a					
	Component					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
The use of electronic payment methods will increase if MaaS is implemented?	.819					
The use of electronic information services e.g. via apps and websites will increase if MaaS is implemented?	.729					
The number of parking space will increase if MaaS is implemented?	.615					
The congestion will decrease if MaaS is implemented?	.523					
The revenues of Urban Transportation Company will increase if MaaS is implemented?		.794				
The big number of trips affects in the implementation of MaaS?		.618				
The long distance of travel affects in the implementation of MaaS?		.606				
The traffic safety will increase if MaaS is implemented?			.717			
The separation of passenger payments between the transport providers will not be a problem if MaaS is implemented?			.651			
The emissions (CO ₂ , NO _x , etc.) will decrease if MaaS is implemented?			.562			
The use of personal vehicle will decrease if MaaS is implemented?			.526			
The perceived stress associated with travelling will decrease if MaaS is implemented?				.790		
The overall satisfaction with transport solution will increase if MaaS is implemented?				.709		
The total cost of travel cost per person per month will decrease if MaaS is implemented?					.775	
The use of walking will increase if MaaS is implemented?					.705	
The passenger number in Urban Bus will increase if MaaS is implemented?						.685
The timetable change will not be a problem for transport companies if MaaS is implemented?						.671
The provision of data by transportation companies will not be a problem if MaaS is implemented?						.630

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.
a. Rotation converged in 7 iterations.

From the above six factors, their average has been calculated and analyzed to determine whether the data have a normal distribution or not, and we have:

Table 4

Descriptive analysis - The average of six factors that derivate from the Factor Analysis

Descriptive			
1	Statistic		Std. Error
The average of six factors that derivate from the Factor Analysis	Mean	4.1679	.04077
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	4.0873
		Upper Bound	4.2486
	5% Trimmed Mean	4.1735	
	Median	4.0000	
	Variance	.218	
	Std. Deviation	.46662	
	Minimum	3.00	
	Maximum	5.00	
	Range	2.00	
	Interquartile Range	.00	
	Skewness	.547	.212
	Kurtosis	.723	.420

The factors Skewness ($0.547 - 0.212 = 0.335$) and Kurtosis ($0.723 - 0.420 = 0.303$) are within the tabular values -1.96 and $+1.96$, therefore, we can say that the data have a normal distribution and can be continued with other analyzes that require this.

The graph is presented in below figure 1.

Fig. 1. The data distribution

Thus, about the questions of the transport operators readiness to join MaaS, as: geographic area; which mode of transport integration would work the best; the type of integration; who should initiate and lead the implementation of MaaS; who should manage the MaaS application; the provision of data by transportation companies; the timetable change; the major obstacle of implementation of MaaS, For all these questions, the distribution of answers in numbers and percentages is presented in the below tables.

Table 5

Presentation of the results about the geographic area: which would be most relevant for the implementation of the MaaS system

Geographic area	Frequency	Percent
Just in Prishtina city	51	38.6
Prishtine dhe Fushe Kosove	50	37.9
Prishtine, Fushe Kosove, Graçanice	17	12.9
Prishtine, Fushe Kosove, Obiliq/ Prishtine, Fushe Kosove, Obiliq	6	4.5
Prishtine, Fushe Kosove, Lipjan/ Prishtine, Fushe Kosove, Lipjan	8	6.1
Total	132	100.0

From the above table, it can be seen that for the area "Prishtina," 51 respondents, or 38.6%, agreed, while it is followed by the area "Prishtina and Fushe Kosova," with 50 respondents, or 37.9%.

Table 6

Presentation of the results about the combination of transport integration ways that would work the best

Combination of transport integration ways	Frequency	Percent
Public/Private Urban Bus, Bicycle, Walk	37	28.0
Public/Private Urban Bus, Bicycle, Taxi, Walk	45	34.1
Public/Private Urban Bus, Bicycle, Train, Walk	21	15.9
Train, Taxi, Bicycle	14	10.6
Train, Urban Bus	11	8.3
Public/Private Urban Bus, Rent a Car, Bicycle	4	3.0
Total	132	100.0

From the table above, it can be seen that for the combination "Public/Private Urban Bus, Bicycle, Taxi, Walk," 45 respondents, or 34.1%, agreed, while 37 respondents, or 28%, were for the combination "Public/Private Urban Bus, Bicycle, Walk."

Table 7

Presentation of the results about the type of integration the most prefer

Type of integration	Frequency	Percent
None	1	.8
Basic level 1	65	49.2
Highest Level 3	66	50.0
Total	132	100.0

The table above shows that depending on the type of transport providers 66 respondents or 50% agree with the third level it may, while 65 respondents or 49.2% initially agreed to implement the first level of integration.

Table 8

Presentation of the data, who should initiate and lead the implementation of MaaS

Type of integration	Frequency	Percent
Local government	100	75.8
Some kind of association of transport providers	6	4.5
Central government	26	19.7
Total	132	100.0

100 out of 132 respondents, or 75.8%, think that the local level is more competent to initiate the implementation of the MaaS service.

Table 9

Presentation of the data related to management with the MaaS application

Combination of transport integration ways	Frequency	Percent
Establishing independent IT company that would provide services for all transport operators	75	56.8
IT MaaS unit within one transport operator, that would provide services for all others	14	10.6
IT MaaS unit as part of local government of Prishtina	43	32.6
Total	132	100.0

75, or 56.8%, of respondents think that the best would be "Establishing independent IT company that would provide services for all transport operators," followed by 43, or 32.6%, with the option "IT MaaS unit as part of the local government of Prishtina".

Based on the results, our recommendation for the implementation of MaaS in Kosovo is to go, first with model 1, then with model 2, as follows:

Model 1:

- Implementation in Prishtina City and Fushe Kosove;
- The modes "public/private urban bus, bicycle, walk"
- The kind of integration "Basic Level 1"
- Local government should initiate and lead the implementation of MaaS;
- IT MaaS unit as part of local government of Prishtina to manage with MaaS application".

Model 2:

- Implementation in "Prishtina City"
- The modes "public/private urban bus, bicycle, taxi, walk"
- The kind of integration "Highest Level 3"
- Local government should initiate and lead the implementation of MaaS;
- Establishing independent IT Company to manage with MaaS application.

CONCLUSION

The results on the survey about the implementation of MaaS in city of Prishtina show that all stakeholders approve it and agree to be a part of this service. They also think that the implementation should be lead at municipal level. The city of Prishtina should initiate, plan and implement the concept of Mobility as a Service. Half of the companies and operators agree with basic level 1: integration of passenger information only, availability of transport services from different modes (time tables, ticket costs, routes, etc.) by internet application, and the other part with level 3: integration of passenger information, coordination of services (time tables, routes, prices), and introduction of one single payment for a multimodal trip (later money will be divided among transport providers by following pre-defined rules of money distribution). They also think that the management of the application should be done by an IT MaaS unit established as part of the local government of Prishtina.

It should also be noted that through this research, the main obstacles to the implementation of this service were identified, such as: illegal taxis, a lack of support from municipal institutions to implement this service, poor provision of internet services, the lack of road and transport infrastructure, the lack of only bus lines, the coordination between operators and the parking spaces, payment sharing, and agreements between operators. Our recommendation for the implementation of MaaS in Kosovo should go, first with model 1, then with model 2, as explained above.

APPENDIX 1. THE QUESTIONNAIRE FOR IMPLEMENTATION OF MAAS (MOBILITY AS A SERVICE) SYSTEM IN PRISHTINA CITY BASIC DATA ON RESPONDER

1. Your address?

2. What type of organization are you?

1. Public transport operator by bus;
2. Private transport operator by bus;
3. Train transport operator;
4. Information and communications technology (ICT) service provider;
5. Taxi service provider;
6. Rent a Car service provider;
7. Rent a Bike service provider.

3. For how long have you worked in the area of transportation?

1. Less than 1 year;
2. 1-5 years;
3. 6-10 years;
4. More than 10 years.

4. Have you ever heard about the concept of MaaS (Mobility as a Service)?

1. Yes,
2. No.

QUESTIONS RELATED TO THE TRANSPORT OPERATORS READINESS TO JOIN MAAS?

5. MaaS (Mobility as a Service) which is aimed to be implementation in Prishtina city, maybe even more beyond, would you agree to be part of the integrated transport system by joining the MaaS system?

1. Yes,
2. No,
3. I am not sure, I need more information.

6. Which geographic area do you consider would be the most relevant for the implementation of MaaS system?

1. Just in Prishtina city;
2. Prishtine dhe Fushe Kosove;
3. Prishtine, Fushe Kosove, Graçanice
4. Prishtine, Fushe Kosove, Obiliq/ Prishtine, Fushe Kosove, Obiliq;
5. Prishtine, Fushe Kosove, Lipjan/ Prishtine, Fushe Kosove, Lipjan
6. Other_____.

7. As a transport provider, what do you think which combination of transport integration ways would work the best?

1. Public/Private Urban Bus, Bicycle, Walk;
2. Public/Private Urban Bus, Bicycle, Taxi, Walk;
3. Public/Private Urban Bus, Bicycle, Train, Walk;
4. Train, Taxi, Bicycle

5. Public/Private Urban Bus, Train.
8. What kind of integration would you prefer?
1. None
 2. Basic level 1 - Integration on the passenger information only, on the availability of transport services from different modes (time tables, ticket cost, routes etc.) by internet application;
 3. Intermediate Level 2 - Integration on passenger information plus coordination of services (timetables, routes, prices) provided by different modes in case of multimodal trip;
 4. Highest Level 3 - Integration on passenger information, coordination of services (timetables, routes, prices) plus introduction of one single payment for a multimodal trip (later money will be divided among transport providers by following pre-defined rules of money distribution).
9. The level 3 integration in the MaaS requires financial and legal arrangements in order to allow single transport ticket payment at one place when a multimodal trip is to be made. Given the current conditions, do you think if this could be done?
1. Yes;
 2. Yes but with major difficulties;
 3. Yes with minor difficulties;
 4. Not possible right now.
10. Do you think that implementation of MaaS should be done in phases (first level 1, then level 2 etc.)
1. Yes;
 2. No;
 3. I don't know.
11. Who do you think should initiate and lead the implementation of MaaS?
1. Local government;
 2. Some kind of association of transport providers;
 3. Central government;
 4. Other (state what)_____.
12. The MaaS system requires IT experts that would manage the MaaS application. What would you prefer?
1. Establishing independent IT company that would provide services for all transport operators
 2. IT MaaS unit within one transport operator, that would provide services for all others
 3. IT MaaS unit as part of local government of Prishtina
 4. If none of above what is your suggestion?
- Please state your suggestion _____

13. The passenger number in Urban Bus will increase if MaaS is implemented?
1. I completely disagree;
 2. I mostly disagree;
 3. Neutral;
 4. I mostly agree;
 5. I completely agree.
14. The provision of data by transportation companies will not be a problem if MaaS is implemented?
1. I completely disagree;
 2. I mostly disagree;
 3. Neutral;
 4. I mostly agree;
 5. I completely agree.
15. The timetable change will not be a problem for transport companies if MaaS is implemented?
1. I completely disagree;
 2. I mostly disagree;
 3. Neutral;
 4. I mostly agree;
 5. I completely agree;
16. The revenues of Urban Transportation Company will increase if MaaS is implemented?
1. I completely disagree;
 2. I mostly disagree;
 3. Neutral;
 4. I mostly agree;
 5. I completely agree.
17. The separation of passenger payments between the transport providers will not be a problem if MaaS is implemented?
1. I completely disagree;
 2. I mostly disagree;
 3. Neutral;
 4. I mostly agree;
 5. I completely agree;
18. The number of trips affects in the implementation of MaaS?
1. I completely disagree;
 2. I mostly disagree;
 3. Neutral;
 4. I mostly agree;
 5. I completely agree.
19. The distance of travelled affects in the implementation of MaaS?
1. I completely disagree;
 2. I mostly disagree;
 3. Neutral;
 4. I mostly agree;
 5. I completely agree.
20. What do you think, which age would use this service the most?
1. 12 – 25;
 2. 26 – 39;
 3. 40 – 55;
 4. 56 – 64;
 5. Over 65.

21. Please tell what do you expect to be major obstacle for introduction MaaS transport services (Please note your opinion):

22. Please tell what do you expect to be major obstacle for one-place payment of transport services (Please note your opinion):

QUESTIONS ABOUT BENEFITS OF MAAS?

23. The travel with Urban Public Bus will increase if MaaS is implemented?

1. I completely disagree;
2. I mostly disagree;
3. Neutral;
4. I mostly agree;
5. I completely agree.

24. The use of walking will increase if MaaS is implemented?

1. I completely disagree;
2. I mostly disagree;
3. Neutral;
4. I mostly agree;
5. I completely agree.

25. The average time of travel will decrease if MaaS is implemented?

1. I completely disagree;
2. I mostly disagree;
3. Neutral;
4. I mostly agree;
5. I completely agree.

26. The use of personal vehicle will decrease if MaaS is implemented?

1. I completely disagree;
2. I mostly disagree;
3. Neutral;
4. I mostly agree;
5. I completely agree.

27. The total cost of travel cost per person per month will decrease if MaaS is implemented?

1. I completely disagree;
2. I mostly disagree;
3. Neutral;
4. I mostly agree;
5. I completely agree.

28. The number of parking space will increase if MaaS is implemented?

1. I completely disagree;
2. I mostly disagree;
3. Neutral;
4. I mostly agree;
5. I completely agree;

29. The congestion will decrease if MaaS is implemented?

1. I completely disagree;
2. I mostly disagree;
3. Neutral;
4. I mostly agree;
5. I completely agree.

30. The traffic safety will increase if MaaS is implemented?

1. I completely disagree;
2. I mostly disagree;
3. Neutral;
4. I mostly agree;
5. I completely agree.

31. The perceived stress associated with travelling will decrease if MaaS is implemented?

1. I completely disagree;
2. I mostly disagree;
3. Neutral;
4. I mostly agree;
5. I completely agree.

32. The overall satisfaction with transport solution will increase if MaaS is implemented?

1. I completely disagree;
2. I mostly disagree;
3. Neutral;
4. I mostly agree;
5. I completely agree.

33. The wellbeing general health will be better if MaaS is implemented?

1. I completely disagree;
2. I mostly disagree;
3. Neutral;
4. I mostly agree;
5. I completely agree.

34. The use of electronic information services e.g. via apps and websites will increase if MaaS is implemented?

1. I completely disagree;
2. I mostly disagree;
3. Neutral;
4. I mostly agree;
5. I completely agree.

35. The use of electronic payment methods will increase if MaaS is implemented?

1. I completely disagree;
2. I mostly disagree;
3. Neutral;
4. I mostly agree;

5. I completely agree.

36. The emissions (CO₂, NO_x, etc.) will decrease if MaaS is implemented?

1. I completely disagree;
2. I mostly disagree;
3. Neutral;
4. I mostly agree;
5. I completely agree.

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